

A trait-based typification of urban forests as nature-based solutions

Sebastian Scheuer^{a,*}, Jessica Jache^a, Martina Kičić^b, Thilo Wellmann^{a,c}, Manuel Wolff^{a,d},
Dagmar Haase^{a,c}

^a Geography Department, Landscape Ecology Lab, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Unter den Linden 6, 10099 Berlin, Germany

^b Croatian Forest Research Institute, Division for International Scientific Cooperation in Southeast Europe, Cvjetno naselje 41, 10450 Jastrebarsko, Croatia

^c UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Computational Landscape Ecology, Permoserstr. 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

^d UFZ – Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, Department of Urban and Environmental Sociology, Permoserstr. 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Dr Cecil Konijnendijk van den Bosch

Keywords:

Urban forest
Nature-based solution
Typology
Trait-based modelling
Semantics
Ontology

ABSTRACT

Urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) are important tools for climate change adaptation and sustainable development. However, achieving both effective and sustainable UF-NBS solutions requires diverse knowledge. This includes knowledge on UF-NBS implementation, on the assessment of their environmental impacts in diverse spatial contexts, and on their management for the long-term safeguarding of delivered benefits. A successful integration of such bodies of knowledge demands a systematic understanding of UF-NBS. To achieve such an understanding, this paper presents a conceptual UF-NBS model obtained through a semantic, trait-based modelling approach. This conceptual model is subsequently implemented as an extendible, re-usable and interoperable ontology. In so doing, a formal, trait-based vocabulary on UF-NBS is created, that allows expressing spatial, morphological, physical, functional, and institutional UF-NBS properties for their typification and a subsequent integration of further knowledge and data. Thereby, ways forward are opened for a more systematic UF-NBS impact assessment, management, and decision-making.

1. Introduction

Urban forest broadly refers to natural and planted trees in cities (Ordóñez and Duinker, 2010). It is understood as tree-dominated urban ecosystems (Berglihn and Gómez-Baggethun, 2021) comprising the entirety of woodlands, groups of trees, and individual trees on public and private land, including street trees, trees within parks or gardens, and even trees on facades or rooftops (Endreny, 2018; FAO, 2016; Konijnendijk, 2003; Ordóñez, 2021; cf. Table 1). Urban forests present themselves as often fragmented and highly diverse in structure and composition, and so, potentially overlap with urban green spaces (UGS) or green-blue infrastructure (GBI) spatially, temporally, or ecologically (Ordóñez, 2021 and Table 1). With urban forests being connected to their wider physical (built) environment alongside social-institutional characteristics, e.g., property relationships, manifold nature-society interactions emerge (Ordóñez and Duinker, 2010).

At the same time, urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) emphasize the importance of tree-based urban ecosystems for human health, human well-being, and biodiversity (Dumitru and Wendling, 2021). In line with nature-based solutions (NBS) as cost-effective, locally

adapted, and systemic interventions for the provisioning of environmental, social, and economic benefits (Almenar et al., 2021; Dumitru and Wendling, 2021; European Commission, 2015; Pauleit et al., 2017), UF-NBS aim at the protection of existing tree stock, the optimization of ecosystem service delivery (Walters and Sinnett, 2021), the greening of cities, e.g., through tree planting initiatives (Doroski et al., 2020; Eisenman et al., 2021), and the engagement of communities to increase urban forest stewardship (Ordóñez, 2021).

Consequently, a typification of UF-NBS must not only embrace such kinds of interventions, but also needs to reflect on site-specific conditions and differences that result from the diverse structure and high spatial heterogeneity of urban forest (Münzinger et al., 2022).

The varied (semi-)natural elements forming UF-NBS deliver manifold benefits through providing ecosystem services, e.g., climate or air quality regulation, the provisioning of raw materials, food and water, or recreational and restorative potential (Ayala-Azcárraga et al., 2019; Berglihn and Gómez-Baggethun, 2021; Marando et al., 2019; Vieira et al., 2018). In so doing, UF-NBS help addressing 15 out of 17 sustainable development goals (Turner-Skoff and Cavender, 2019). This renders UF-NBS important tools to make cities more resilient, more

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: sebastian.scheuer@geo.hu-berlin.de (S. Scheuer).

Table 1

Competency questions to facilitate the identification of core concepts and relationships for guiding the further conceptualization of the proposed ontology. Answers to each question are based on expert knowledge and the analysis of the state-of-the-art. Core concepts to guide the further conceptualization of UF-NBS are printed in italics.

Competency question	Answer
What is urban forest?	<i>Urban forest</i> refers to tree-dominated ecosystems within cities (Berglihn and Gómez-Baggethun, 2021). This includes <i>forests, clusters or groups of trees</i> , as well as <i>solitary trees</i> in public and private spaces and across different types of urban green spaces such as <i>parks, gardens, on facades, or rooftops</i> (Endreny, 2018; FAO, 2016; Konijnendijk, 2003; Ordóñez, 2021).
What is urban green space (UGS)?	Here, <i>UGS</i> are referred to as natural or semi-natural land in urban areas, i.e., vegetated plots including agricultural areas, <i>lawns, forests, parks, gardens</i> (Collins et al., 2022; WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2016).
What is green-blue infrastructure (GBI)?	<i>GBI</i> is understood as natural or semi-natural <i>landscape elements</i> , that (may) form an interrelated green-blue network across different spatial scales (Langemeyer and Baró, 2021; Vlaamse Land Maatschappij, 2019).
What is a nature-based solution (NBS)?	<i>NBS</i> are <i>action-oriented, cost-effective, locally adapted, systemic interventions supported by nature for a simultaneous provisioning of environmental, social, and economic benefits to build resilience</i> (Almenar et al., 2021; Dumitru and Wendling, 2021; European Commission, 2015; Pauleit et al., 2017). <i>NBS</i> aim at the <i>protection, management, or restoration of ecosystem services</i> to provide benefits to society and biodiversity (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016; Hanson et al. 2020). <i>NBS</i> may also be understood as an umbrella term that is related to and evolves neighbouring concepts, including urban forestry, UGS, and GBI, and <i>ecosystem services</i> (Dumitru and Wendling, 2021; Pauleit et al., 2017).
What is an urban forest as nature-based solution (UF-NBS)?	<i>UF-NBS</i> build on tree-based urban ecosystems to address societal challenges, and their importance for human well-being and biodiversity (Dumitru and Wendling, 2021). <i>UF-NBS</i> are closely related to the urban forest as a spatial entity, and to actions for the expansion, protection, and maintenance of the urban forest.
What are specific types of UF-NBS to be covered by the proposed UF-NBS typology?	The proposed typology needs to account for <i>UF-NBS</i> as spatial entities, and urban forest-related actions. <i>UF-NBS</i> to be covered include <i>urban forests, tree clusters</i> , and types such as <i>street trees, or promenades</i> , as well as trees located in urban parks or gardens. <i>UF-NBS</i> as actions include <i>afforestation, reforestation, tree planting</i> , or the <i>monitoring</i> of trees and forests. In addition to these <i>UF-NBS</i> in a narrower sense, we also consider the spatial context of these <i>UF-NBS</i> as relevant. This particularly includes <i>UGS</i> , as potentially tree-dominated urban ecosystems (Orti et al., 2022).
Which traits are relevant to describe UF-NBS?	Traits must be able to describe <i>spatial, morphological, structural, functional, or institutional</i> characteristics. Factors governing the biophysical properties of <i>UF-NBS</i> , i.e., <i>tree traits</i> , need to be considered. Covered traits must also be suitable to contextualize mediating factors. This includes spatial relationships, e.g., <i>adjacency</i> . Grouping principles applied in

Table 1 (continued)

Competency question	Answer
What is a forest?	top-down typologies help to identify further traits. A <i>forest</i> may be understood as an <i>area</i> that is at least 0.5 ha in <i>size</i> (FAO, 2018), and that is covered by and thus dominated by trees. Janssen and Rosu (2015) suggest a <i>canopy cover</i> of at least 50 % for the delineation of such <i>treed areas</i> . This threshold may currently be observed, or yet to be reached.

liveable, and healthier (Endreny, 2018; FAO, 2016).

However, this ecosystem service delivery is mediated by urban morphology and form, including land-use heterogeneity, fragmentation, and use intensity, and subsequently, by the composition, shape, size, persistence, and interconnectivity of green elements (Alberti, 2005; Holt et al., 2015; Steenberg et al., 2015). Ecosystem service delivery of tree-based ecosystems is further mediated by the state and dimension of trees with respect to height, width, connectivity, and species diversity; soil conditions; the proximity to buildings and infrastructures; the location within street canyons or open structures of different size; accessibility; and tree maintenance (Cimburova and Berghauser Pont, 2021).

For a typification of UF-NBS, this calls once more for a close consideration of site-specific conditions and spatial and contextual relationships of UF-NBS with their physical, social, and ecological environment, to support the estimation of their material and immaterial benefits, and to make UF-NBS more comprehensive entities. It is furthermore argued that for best outcomes of UF-NBS action, a multi-functional perspective on UF-NBS should be adopted (Ordóñez, 2021). To do so, again, a systematic understanding of their (small-scale) impacts is needed.

1.1. Objectives of this paper

Against this background, this paper challenges the complexity of typifying UF-NBS that emerges from the spatial and structural diversity of urban forests, and from the manifold actions related to them, through a trait-based modelling approach. In trait-based modelling, traits are understood as morphological, physiological, phenological, biochemical, or structural characteristics of individual organisms with impact to their fitness or to ecosystem properties (Violle et al., 2007; Wellmann et al., 2018; Zakharova et al., 2019). Furthermore, Andersson et al. (2021) propose the concept of social-ecological traits, that “[...] shape [...] ecological systems and linked human affordances [...], and social systems by shaping the context of human activities and experiences”. Expanding on these notions, here, a trait is understood as a discernible aggregate feature of UF-NBS including spatial, morphological, contextual, structural, functional, and institutional characteristics.

Therefore, to advance the state-of-the-art, contingent on such traits, and complemented by semantic modelling, i.e., the systematic structuring of knowledge through the identification of relevant concepts and the modelling of their taxonomy, interrelationships, and properties (Villa et al., 2009), this paper develops a systematic, trait-based UF-NBS typology.

Thereby, in seeking to provide a common, more comprehensive understanding of UF-NBS, first, a conceptual UF-NBS model including a vocabulary of terms is being devised, to enable a trait-based description and to drive a subsequent definition of UF-NBS. The following section explores the state-of-the-art to support the development of this conceptual model. Second, as explained in the sections thereafter, through the operationalization of this conceptual model in form of an ontology, a machine-readable, machine-interpretable, re-usable and extendible knowledge representation is created (Gašević et al., 2006). In so doing,

on the one hand, the conceptual UF-NBS model shall be transformed into a knowledge body that may be queried, and reasoned upon, using different software tools. On the other hand, formal anchor points for a later integration of knowledge and data shall be established, to facilitate UF-NBS assessment and governance, and to allow for the accommodation of a growing body of research.

2. Exploring state-of-the-art typologies for kick-starting ontology development

The implementation of the proposed UF-NBS typology requires an identification of relevant UF-NBS. As stated previously, UF-NBS are closely related with UGS, GBI, and NBS (cf. Table 1 for definitions). Hence, exploring typologies related to those concepts may assist in the elicitation of different UF-NBS types and traits, and in determining the role, part-taking, or overlaps of UGS, GBI, and NBS as contextual entities with UF-NBS. There are several typologies seeking to provide a systematic grouping of UGS, GBI and NBS, that recognize the multiple (co-) benefits provided by urban greenery and associated challenges. Broadly, these typologies may be grouped into *top-down* and *bottom-up* typologies.

Top-down typologies are commonly based on classification principles that reflect on spatial, physical, functional or governance characteristics for grouping UGS, GBI or NBS. The GREEN SURGE typology proposes various UGS types, e.g., “private, commercial, industrial, institutional UGS and UGS connected to grey infrastructure” or “parks and recreation”, and collates empirical evidence for the delivery of provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting ecosystem services (Cvejić et al., 2015). Its focus is on spatial entities of UGS and associated benefits, thus neglecting NBS in the form of interventions. Such interventions are explored by Eggermont et al. (2015), suggesting a classification of NBS along three main categories: (i) minimal-intervention NBS seeking to maintain or improve the delivery of ecosystem services by given ecosystems; (ii) the development of management approaches for sustainable and multifunctional ecosystems; and (iii) the intrusive management or creation of novel ecosystems, inclusive of specific UGS types. Furthering these NBS categories, the ThinkNature typology recommends explicit actions and strategies for different types of UGS or desired benefits, including management practices, planning guidelines, monitoring actions, or restoration interventions (Nikolaidis et al., 2019). In a similar vein, the Nature4Cities typology employs an analytical framework that recognizes a level of human intervention for NBS; urban challenges; spatio-temporal scales; and physical environment (Nature4Cities, 2018). Embedded in this framework, Nature4Cities (2018) examines NBS actions and strategies as well as NBS construction and design principles.

In contrast, *bottom-up typologies* use trait-based modelling approaches to derive green elements as a function of local conditions and traits. For example, based on an ecosystem classification approach, Steenberg et al. (2015) propose a categorization schema of traits combined with hierarchical clustering for the identification of urban forest types in the city of Toronto. In their typology, traits include biophysical properties, e.g., grass or tree canopy cover, built environment factors such as building coverage, and social indicators. Similarly, Kok et al. (2016) elaborate a green infrastructure typology that abstracts land-cover, structural-morphological features, and spatial-configurational arrangements, such as solitary or clustered vegetational elements. Green infrastructure types, e.g., vegetated surfaces or intensive green roofs, are subsequently derived from the permutation of these traits.

When comparing these types of typologies broadly, it becomes clear that bottom-up examples tend to be based on specific traits, but lack an overarching action context or institutional aspects that are recognized as important governance challenges for NBS (Ordóñez, 2021). Contrary to that, top-down typologies tend to consider such a governance dimension, as well as manifold grouping principles, but lack to conceptualize

mediating local conditions more closely. Hence, the integration of trait-based, bottom-up approaches with the grouping principles and the governance focus of top-down typologies is where the state-of-the-art is picked up in conceptualizing the proposed UF-NBS typology.

3. Methodology

Semantic modelling for ontology implementation is also referred to as ontology building. There are several ontology building methodologies that typically comprise the specification of scope and purpose, including a review of existing knowledge; the conceptualization; and the formalization, implementation, testing, evaluation, and maintenance of knowledge (Gómez-Pérez et al., 2004; Uschold and King, 1995). The methodology for implementing the proposed UF-NBS typology as an ontology closely mirrors these steps (Fig. 1 A).

3.1. Specification

In line with the objectives of this paper, the proposed ontology's scope and purpose is the implementation of a conceptual model on UF-NBS for promoting human health and well-being, including a reflection on the relationships between UF-NBS and NBS, as well as UGS and GBI as important enablers of citizen's health and well-being. The review of existing knowledge was assisted by competency questions that recapitulate key questions for the discovery and structuring of knowledge (Sure et al., 2009). These competency questions were answered through exploring the state-of-the-art, including the typologies outlined above, as well as a review of 422 records on the benefits of UF-NBS for livability, public health, and biodiversity (Scheuer et al., 2021a and Fig. S1). The development was further supported by expert knowledge on (urban) forestry, e.g., involving the European Forest Institute and the Croatian Forest Research Institute.

3.2. Conceptualization

The conceptualization phase corresponds to the actual semantic modelling process. Here, a middle-out strategy is followed (Fig. 1B). Supported by the exploration of the state-of-the-art as part of the specification phase, the middle-out strategy suggests the elicitation of an initial set of core concepts as a starting point (Gómez-Pérez et al., 2004; Uschold and Grüninger, 1996), with their taxonomy, interrelationships, and traits to subsequently be modelled. Simultaneously, through an abstraction and generalization of concepts, or through their further specification and detailing, additional relevant concepts may be identified, and added to the conceptual model as deemed necessary by the modeller (Fig. 1B). This process is repeated until the conceptual model meets the specified scope and purpose. The resulting conceptual UF-NBS model is subsequently formalized and implemented.

3.3. Formalization, implementation, testing, and evaluation

Knowledge formalization and implementation describes the process of transforming the conceptual UF-NBS model into formal knowledge by means of an ontology language. Here, the *Web Ontology Language (OWL) version 2* is chosen, as it provides a rich vocabulary for the modelling of concepts, properties and (taxonomic) relationships (Hitzler et al., 2012). The implementation is conducted using *Ontarion Fluent Editor* by *Cognitum*. This tool simplifies ontology building through the *Ontarion Controlled Natural Language (OCNL)*, i.e., a comparatively easy to understand but machine-executable syntax that is internally translated into OWL constructs (Kapłański, 2011; Seganti et al., 2016).

Using *Ontarion Fluent Editor*, the so-implemented typology is continuously checked for syntactic correctness, i.e., that it remains computable for inference and reasoning, and based on test cases, evaluated for consistency, to ensure that it is in accordance with the conceptual UF-NBS model. A further evaluation of the implemented

Fig. 1. Building the proposed UF-NBS ontology comprises the phases of specification; conceptualization; and knowledge formalization, implementation, testing, and evaluation (A). The scope- and purpose-driven conceptualization of UF-NBS knowledge is a core activity of ontology building. Here, conceptualization is supported by a middle-out strategy as shown on the right (B). Ellipses in green exemplify an initial set of core concepts, with their characteristics and interrelationships being modelled, e.g., functional traits (1) or spatial relationships (2). Simultaneously, e.g., from expert knowledge, guided by competency questions, or through abstraction and generalization, further UF-NBS-relevant concepts are subsequently identified (3), resulting in a concept taxonomy (4). Similarly, through concept specification and detailing (5), further relevant concepts may also be derived (6). This process is iterative and is repeated until the conceptual model is in line with the scope and purpose of the ontology.

Fig. 2. UF-NBS are conceptualized as the intersection of NBS with urban forest(try), and are considered multidimensional entities that embrace a governance, spatial-morphological, and functional dimension. Each dimension is specified based on traits. Within the governance dimension, traits build activities, that are, in turn, parts of actions. The spatial-morphological dimension comprises trait-based landscape elements, that serve as building blocks of GBI. GBI, in turn, correspond to spatial entities that may subsequently be detailed by further traits. The functional dimension devises a (potential) delivery of ecosystem services that is grounded in biophysical processes and functions, with ecosystem services delivery being considered key for successful NBS.

typology is conducted through a series of webinars and stakeholder workshops.

4. Results

Consultation of the state-of-the-art allowed answering a set of competency questions (Table 1) for kickstarting ontology building and knowledge conceptualization, i.e., to guide the elicitation and definition of core concepts, to aid in formulating their interrelationships, and thus, to structure UF-NBS knowledge.

Overall, here, UF-NBS are defined as the formal intersection of NBS and the urban forest concept (Fig. 2). Therefore, their conceptualization is guided by an understanding of NBS as a broad umbrella term, aligned to urban forest(try). For this purpose, NBS are considered multidimensional entities, including the dimensions of (i) governance, i.e., a broad action and challenge orientation inclusive of institutional aspects, stewardship, participation etc.; (ii) function, i.e., a relation to biophysical processes, and ecosystem services delivery; and (iii) morphology and space, i.e., the adoption of spatial, contextual, and morphological characteristics (Fig. 2).

Subsequently, relationships are formalized to link the different dimensions. Actions are reckoned to target given spatial entities in seeking the delivery of benefits, thus associating governance action with the functional and the spatial-morphological dimension. These latter two dimensions are linked by viewing (semi-)natural landscape elements, and hence GBI elements, to (potentially) deliver ecosystem services as a function of biophysical processes, as mediated by their morphology, composition, site-specific conditions, and local spatial contexts.

Moreover, each of the NBS dimensions represents a rather generic notion, thus requiring further specification. Therefore, each dimension is understood as a “combination of properties”, or “composition of things”, respectively, that is constructed bottom-up through combining relevant concepts and traits. For example, afforestation action is understood to comprise tree planting activity. Likewise, trees are regarded as (green) landscape elements, i.e., as spatial entities that serve as building blocks of forest as a type of GBI.

There are three entry points emerging from this framing (Fig. 2): (i) a traits entry point as a “starting point” for the elicitation of traits to drive the trait-based modelling of UF-NBS inclusive of the postulated NBS dimensions; (ii) a “top-down” entry point that is related to ecosystem services as well as UF-NBS types identified a-priori, as modelling “end points”; and (iii) a “bottom-up” entry point, that is concerned with the description of the aforementioned “end points” with the help of traits. Therefore, this entry point puts the trait-based modelling into operation.

4.1. The traits entry point

The ontology proposes various traits for the expression of spatial context, morphology, form, and of physical, structural, functional, or institutional characteristics. A set of properties allows to express spatial context through spatial-topological relationships by stating adjacency, (full) enclosure, or part-taking of entities. Morphology and form may be conveyed in a two-fold manner: (i) through expressing the grouping of objects as solitary, linear, or clustered. For clustered arrangements, regular and irregular grouping patterns are considered to reflect on different vegetation structures (Lehmann et al., 2014); and (ii) through describing the composition of entities, e.g., being inclusive of trees, shrubs, water bodies, or amenity features. Traits for the description of physical location include being ground-based, being associated with support structures, e.g., potted, or being located on balconies and rooftops. Function is denoted through the contribution of entities to biophysical processes and/or functions, e.g., evaporation or active recreational use, and with ecosystem services delivery, e.g., regulation of air temperature and humidity or recreation, then being inferred from transitive relationships. Regarding governance and institutional context, e.g., institutional accessibility including public, semi-public, selective

private, or temporally (un-)restricted access, and entitlement schemes—e.g., unrestricted public use, restricted collective use, or restricted private use—are formalized (Nissen, 2008). Further traits related to actions as a form of governance are devised to assert their spatial context, i.e., the target area of interventions, and to express involved activities.

4.2. The top-down entry-point

As stated above, the top-down entry point subsumes “end points” for modelling. Regarding ecosystem services, the ontology formalizes several supporting services, provisioning services, regulation and maintenance services, and cultural ecosystem services. Regarding actions and GBI elements as prospective UF-NBS, in line with the paper’s objectives, several types were identified:

- As actions: afforestation, reforestation, orchard restoration, enrichment planting, tree and forest monitoring, tree pruning, tree watering, and pest management.
- As spatial (GBI) entities: forests, riparian forests, nurseries, and forest plantations; elements of the urban food forest, e.g., orchards; elements associated with urban networks, e.g., street trees or tree alleys; greenery associated with buildings or built-up structures, e.g., green roofs, green facades, or atria; and UGS types such as parks, gardens, and cemeteries, that may pose specific or contextual UF-NBS entities, e.g., depending on their composition.

Furthermore, reflecting on the classification of NBS suggested by Eggermont et al. (2015), the typology proposes the grouping of actions depending on their outcome or intention, i.e., a grouping based on whether an action seeks to provide additional benefits through the construction of novel UF-NBS; the improvement of ecosystem service delivery of current UF-NBS through restoration; or the long-term safeguarding and maintenance of ecosystem service delivery through appropriate UF-NBS management (Smith et al., 2016).

4.3. The bottom-up entry point

In line with the notion of (UF-)NBS dimensions as “compositions of things”, the bottom-up entry point puts the trait-based modelling of concepts into operation. Thus, following the middle-out strategy, concepts are modelled bottom-up through the assignment of relevant combinations of spatial, morphological, functional, or institutional traits, and by their relationships with other concepts. Through a subsequent combination of suchlike constructed entities, increasingly higher-level concepts are devised, that may be re-used iteratively as building blocks for further entities, until the UF-NBS “end points” identified top-down are sufficiently defined.

With respect to the governance dimension, building blocks of actions are defined in the form of so-called activities. Exemplarily, activities include the planting of trees or shrubs, pest control, pruning, or monitoring. In a similar way, building blocks of the spatial-morphological dimension encompass various green, blue, and grey (built-up) landscape elements. Green landscape elements comprise vegetational elements, i.e., woody and non-woody vegetation, and thus grass, shrub, or trees. Rather than relying on this generic and abstract notion, traits such as genus or species, age, leaf area index, etc. may also be designated. Higher-level building blocks are then derived through a further allocation of traits. For instance, a single tree is derived by attributing a solitary grouping to the tree concept, whilst a grove is devised as a clustered group of trees. Edible plants, including fruit trees, may be inferred from food production as functional trait. Blue landscape elements conceptualize watercourses, e.g., rivers or canals, or permanent bodies of standing water, such as ponds. Grey landscape elements comprise elements from the built environment, including houses or (multistorey) buildings, urban network elements such as paths, tracks,

or streets, and selected amenity features, e.g., sports fields, playgrounds etc., with functional or institutional traits being added as needed, e.g., to indicate accessibility or entitlements of use.

4.4. The synergy of the three perspectives

In the following, exemplified for (riparian) forests, single street trees, neighbourhood green spaces, tree watering, and afforestation, it will be described how all entry points are brought together, and therefore, how traits, and thus the trait-based vocabulary provided by the proposed ontology, assist in a systematic characterisation of UF-NBS.

Following the competency questions (Table 1), a forest is understood

as a treed area of specific size. Consequently, first, treed area is conceptualized as being composed of trees, that are ground-based, grouped in a two-dimensional manner, and arranged so that at least 50 % of the area is (or will potentially be) covered by tree canopy (Fig. 3 A). Subsequently, the forest definition is completed by re-using the treed area concept, and by adding a size constraint of at-least 0.5 ha. Further traits, e.g., functional traits such as the production of timber, may be added if applicable for the entity in question (Fig. 3B). Fig. 3 C exemplifies how further types of forest may in turn be formalized. For instance, here, riparian forest is derived from forest by adding traits describing adjacency to a river, and impact by flooding as a physical phenomenon. Re-using known concepts as building blocks,

Fig. 3. Definition of UF-NBS through trait-based modelling. Treed areas are derived through the assignment of traits describing composition, physical location, grouping of elements, and canopy cover; here, either observed values or potential canopy cover yet to be reached may be considered (A). Forests are in turn derived from treed areas by adding a size constraint, with functional traits being added if applicable (B). Different types of forest may subsequently be distinguished. Here, riparian forest is derived from added traits describing adjacency and impact by physical phenomena (C). Similarly, through the re-use of building blocks, single street trees may be inferred from ground-based trees, with traits added to express solitary grouping and adjacency to street (D). Through the description of spatial context, and by capturing institutional characteristics, further types of GBI, e.g., neighbourhood green spaces, may be conceptualized. Those may pose UF-NBS themselves or provide site-specific context to UF-NBS entities. (E). Actions are formalized based on involved activities, e.g., watering, and by pointing at the entities they are aimed e.g., tree, here, resulting in tree watering as UF-NBS action. (F). Similarly, by targeting a spatial entity (of any kind) for planting of trees, and by additionally stating the goal of this activity as seeking to implement a forest, afforestation may be denoted (G).

single street trees may be described as ground-based, solitary trees adjacent to streets (Fig. 3D). Similarly, neighbourhood green spaces may be conceptualized, e.g., as compositions of different types of green landscape elements such as lawns and trees, and with further spatial-topological (adjacency) and institutional (institutional accessibility) traits being added (Fig. 3E). Depending on their morphological characteristics, such entities may subsequently pose UF-NBS themselves, or may contextualize site-specific conditions as important mediators of UF-NBS function. Likewise, using activities as building blocks, actions as types of UF-NBS are expressed by denoting their goals and/or their spatial context. For instance, tree watering as UF-NBS action is formalized by linking watering activity to trees (Fig. 3 F), and afforestation action is devised to comprise tree planting activity that is aimed at a given spatial entity to implement a forest (Fig. 3 G).

The so-conceptualized UF-NBS model was subsequently formalized and implemented using OCNL. As exemplified in Fig. 4, OCNL provides pre-defined syntactic elements, printed in blue, that are used in conjunction with the self-defined, trait-based UF-NBS vocabulary, printed in black, to formally express UF-NBS knowledge (Fig. 4). The complete implementation, including a full listing of OCNL statements, is described in more detail in Scheuer et al. (2021b).

The implemented ontology is visualized in Fig. 5 in the form of a semantic network, i.e., a (directed) graph structure depicting concepts, their properties, and (taxonomic) interrelationships. Here, concepts are visualized as yellow rectangles. Green rectangles denote instances of concepts, e.g., types of ecosystem services or specific trait expressions such as ground-based, with dashed black edges indicating their corresponding concept membership. Purple edges show taxonomic and semantic relationships, e.g., equivalency, and solid black edges correspond to formalized traits.

To conclude ontology building, the implemented ontology was sought to be evaluated in a series of virtual events, with particular focus on the underlying conceptual UF-NBS model. First, in a set of webinars, initial feedback was collected from consortium members, to ensure a shared understanding of concepts. Second, to obtain wider critique on the devised conceptual model, a public workshop was held. For this event, a broad audience of 119 stakeholders registered with institutional backgrounds from city administration, education and research, environmental networks, to environmental charities. Stakeholders were invited to discuss the trait-based approach, as well as potential avenues for dissemination and re-use. Thereby, further potentially relevant traits and UF-NBS types could be identified (Fig. S3). Following the middle-out strategy, these candidate concepts may serve as core concepts, i.e., starting point, in a subsequent ontology building iteration.

5. Discussion and conclusions

By developing an ontology for the typification of UF-NBS, the work described in this paper is seen to advance the state-of-the-art in distinct

ways. First, in contrast to rather narrative/textual definitions, trait-based and semantic modelling was used to approach the grouping of UF-NBS. By the simultaneous consideration of top-down and bottom-up approaches, a vocabulary of terms was elaborated that, based on conceptualized traits, enables the expression of defining spatial-morphological, functional, and institutional characteristics, thereby driving the systematization of UF-NBS knowledge.

In so doing, first, on the one hand, a consensual understanding of UF-NBS terms including their interrelationships is being developed, that may foster knowledge transfer and help bridging language or cultural barriers (Taylor and Hochuli, 2017). Similarly, (interdisciplinary) stakeholder discussion and decision-making may be facilitated by such a shared understanding. On the other hand, by allowing for an expression of site-specific conditions and spatial context, local factors mediating UF-NBS function and associated benefits may be reflected more systematically, with potential overlaps of UF-NBS with UGS and GBI being uncovered. By further expressing individual UF-NBS properties regarding vegetational structure, choice of tree species, tree age, or amount of greenery, etc., standardized UF-NBS inventories may be built that, based on a common language, depict the actual heterogeneity and diversity of UF-NBS and their embedding into the urban fabric to assist assessment, management, planning, and informed decision-making (Zürcher, 2017) as key to sustainable urban forestry (Dwyer et al., 2003). Thereby, the perception of UF-NBS as social-ecological systems (SES) is also being stressed. SES characterize UF-NBS not only by their natural components that govern biophysical functions and processes but emphasize the interactions and mutual impacts of these natural components with a co-evolving, multi-actor social subsystem (Fischer, 2018; Vogt, 2020). In this regard, as highlighted by Andersson et al. (2021), social-ecological traits mediate social experiences and human affordances, thus, the presence of features like playgrounds or sports facilities is seen to embody associated recreative benefits. In line with calls to establish broader definitions of GBI that focus more closely on the interrelationships between the natural and built environment in the production of ecological or societal benefits (Grabowski et al., 2022), the devised work adequacy formalizes such transitive dependencies of form and function.

Second, through the implementation of this shared, conceptual understanding as an ontology, a formal, extendible, machine-readable, and machine-interpretable knowledge representation is created, that permits conducting reasoning and inference on UF-NBS knowledge such as the aforementioned inventories. In so doing, e.g., fuzzy relationships that result from underlying traits may be identified. For instance, depending on morphology, form, and institutional characteristics, spatial entities may pose polymorphic subjects that correspond to several UF-NBS types simultaneously, thus speaking to their multi-functional character (Ordóñez, 2021). By this means, rather generic land-use categories such as “urban green space” may be augmented by inferred (polymorphic) UF-NBS types and their respective traits, to

Fig. 4. Formalization of conceptual UF-NBS knowledge using OCNL, exemplified for the treed area concept. OCNL syntactic elements are printed in blue, whereas devised traits and concepts, i.e., the vocabulary as provided by the proposed typology, is printed in black.

Fig. 5. Semantic network of the proposed UF-NBS ontology. Concepts are visualized as yellow rectangles, and instances of concepts as green rectangles. Coloured edges indicate semantic interrelationships. Notably, purple edges denote taxonomic relations. Membership is indicated by dashed black edges, and formalized traits by solid black edges. Please refer to Fig. S2 for an enlarged version.

support modelling of SES and the assessment of site-specific impacts. Thereby, also opportunities for learning, knowledge exchange, and sustainable management are opened. For example, factors for success or failure of UF-NBS may be more readily identified based on traits, thus assisting in the optimization of UF-NBS selection and design to obtain more-sustainable solutions to socio-environmental challenges.

In perspective, starting from there, knowledge-based decision-support tools may then be devised. However, to support such broader scopes, a refinement particularly of governance concepts will be required, e.g., to cover aspects such as participation, cost (-effectiveness), or actions aiming at the change of certain traits, e.g., accessibility. The ontology’s scope may also be furthered, and hence, its re-usability increased, by an extension with a technological dimension, that emphasizes how technology mediates social-environmental interactions and alters human agency (Ahlborg et al., 2019). In so doing, the ontology may be aligned with other trait-based frameworks or third-party ontologies, thereby, promoting the discovery of relevant knowledge and data. For example, Lausch et al. (2016) review trait-based indicators of forest health, stress and disturbances, and Vogt (2020) summarizes traits on the sustainability of urban forests related to vegetational characteristics and community and resource management. Battle and Kolas (2012) propose the GeoSPARQL ontology for the semantic representation and querying of geospatial data, and Aldana-Martín et al. (2022) propose the RESEO earth observation ontology to formalize remote-sensing data and products. In this regard, through included tree traits, the ontology already provides anchor points for the integration of databases on tree-related impacts such as i-Tree (Nowak et al., 2018). Thereby, linkage of relevant data, and thus, impact

assessment shall be facilitated.

However, there are limitations to the presented approach. Particularly when compared to top-down typologies, a lack of distinguishing traits or shared understanding may result in a limited expressiveness. For example, due to these reasons, pocket parks as frequently mentioned elements of top-down typologies could not be considered. On a more general note, this touches on issues of scalability, that needs to be critically reflected considering the desired scope. As mentioned, the typology, and thus, the provided vocabulary of terms, focus primarily on (compositions of) UF-NBS entities for the delivery of human health and well-being benefits. Therefore, the ontology is directed at individual or grouped entities, e.g., trees or tree lines, and at compositions thereof, e.g., forests or urban parks, that correspond to scope-dependent, top-down-derived modelling “end-points”. Although the grouping principles outlined in the typology may also be applied to these entities, thereby deriving compositions at increasingly smaller spatial scales, e.g., city districts, the vocabulary of terms is seen to lack the required expressiveness to do so systematically, e.g., regarding use of built-up land etc.

Further limitations arise from certain open-ended specifications of UF-NBS traits. This applies, e.g., to the canopy cover threshold used in the definition of treed areas, and subsequently, forest. The chosen value is significantly higher when compared to the definition by FAO (2018). However, it approximates closed forest (>40 % canopy cover; Colson et al., 2009) and the UNESCO forest terminology (>60 % canopy cover; cf. Romijn et al., 2013), and with respect to the urban context that is in focus, the threshold chosen appears to be rather reasonable, with an average canopy of already 56 % reported for (European) UGS (Ortí et al., 2022). Clearly, these thresholds highlight the fuzziness of concepts. For

example, changes in forest stock that result from differing thresholds, or therefore, forest definitions, could be explored by their adaptation. Moreover, in the case of UGS, e.g., it is only expressed that these concepts feature a certain institutional accessibility, but no specific mode of accessibility is universally defined. This is because it may only be possible to express such traits for actual UF-NBS instances. To exemplify, looking at examples of UGS in Berlin, Germany, there are those featuring public, free, and temporally unrestricted access (e.g., Treptower Park), whereas others feature public, free but temporally restricted access (e.g., Tempelhofer Feld), and yet others featuring public but temporally restricted and at-cost access (e.g., Gärten der Welt). This emphasizes once more that for the production of benefits, such site-specific, local conditions must be considered, as they may vary significantly between different instances of UF-NBS. It has been shown that the proposed approach allows for their consideration, and in so doing, provides anchor points for more specific research.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

Funding: Sebastian Scheuer, Dagmar Haase, Manuel Wolff and Thilo Wellmann were supported by the CLEARING HOUSE (Collaborative Learning in Research, Information-sharing and Governance on How Urban tree-based solutions support Sino-European urban futures) Horizon 2020 project (grant no. 821242). Sebastian Scheuer, Jessica Jache and Dagmar Haase were supported by the GreenCityLabHue Project (FKZ 01LE1910A1). Martina Kičić is supported by the Croatian Science Foundation, CULTUR-ES project (Improving green infrastructure planning and management through participatory mapping of cultural ecosystem services, grant no. UIP-2017-05-1986). Thilo Wellmann receives a scholarship from the Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt (DBU; German Federal Environmental Foundation).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sebastian Scheuer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization **Jessica Jache:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Validation, Writing – review & editing **Martina Kičić:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing **Manuel Wolff:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing **Thilo Wellmann:** Writing – review & editing **Dagmar Haase:** Conceptualization, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127780](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2022.127780).

References

- Ahlborg, H., Ruiz-Mercado, I., Molander, S., Masera, O., 2019. Bringing technology into social-ecological systems research—motivations for a socio-technical-ecological systems approach. *Sustainability* 11 (7), 2009.
- Alberti, M., 2005. The effects of urban patterns on ecosystem function. *Int. Reg. Sci. Rev.* 28 (2), 168–192.
- Aldana-Martín, J., García-Nieto, J., del Mar Roldán-García, M., Aldana-Montes, J., 2022. Semantic modelling of earth observation remote sensing. *Expert Syst. Appl.* 187, 115838.
- Almenar, J., Elliot, T., Rugani, B., Philippe, B., Gutierrez, T., Sonnemann, G., Geneletti, D., 2021. Nexus between nature-based solutions, ecosystem services and urban challenges. *Land Use Policy* 100, 104898.
- Andersson, E., Haase, H., Anderson, P., Cortinovis, C., Goodness, J., Kendal, D., Lausch, A., McPhearson, T., Sikorska, D., Wellmann, T., 2021. What are the traits of

- a social-ecological system: towards a framework in support of urban sustainability. *npj Urban Sustain.* 1 (14) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-020-00008-4>.
- Ayala-Azcárraga, C., Diaz, D., Zambrano, L., 2019. Characteristics of urban parks and their relation to user well-being. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 189, 27–35.
- Battle, R., Kolas, D., 2012. Enabling the geospatial semantic web with parliament and GeoSPARQL. *Semant. Web* 3, 355–370.
- Berglihn, E.C., Gómez-Baggethun, E., 2021. Ecosystem services from urban forests: the case of Oslomarka, Norway. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 51, 101358.
- Cimburowa, Z., Berghauer Pont, M., 2021. Location matters. A systematic review of spatial contextual factors mediating ecosystem services of urban trees. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 50, 101296.
- Cohen-Shacham, E., Walters, G., Janzen, C., Maginnis, S. (Eds.), 2016. *Nature-Based Solutions to Address Global Societal Challenges*. IUCN, Gland.
- Collins, C., Haase, D., Heiland, S., Kabisch, N., 2022. Urban green space interaction and wellbeing – investigating the experience of international students in Berlin during the first COVID-19 lockdown. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 70, 127543.
- Colson, F., Bogaert, J., Filho, A., Nelson, B., Pinagó, E., Ceulemans, R., 2009. The influence of forest definition on landscape fragmentation assessment in Rondonia, Brazil. *Ecol. Indic.* 9, 1163–1168.
- Cvejić, R., Eler, K., Pintar, M., Železnikar, Š., Haase, D., Kabisch, N., & Strohbach, M., 2015. A typology of urban green spaces, eco-system services provisioning services and demands. EU FP7 (ENV.2013.6.2–5-603567) GREEN SURGE project (2013–2017). Retrieved January 22nd, 2020 from (<http://www.e-pages.dk/ku/1334/html5/>).
- Doroski, D., Ashton, M., Duguid, M.C., 2020. The future urban forest – a survey of tree planting programs in the Northeastern United States. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 55, 126816.
- Dwyer, J., Nowak, D., Noble, M., 2003. Sustainable urban forests. *J. Arboric.* 29 (1), 49–55.
- Eisenman, T.A., Flanders, T., Harper, R.W., Hauer, R.J., Lieberknecht, K., 2021. Traits of a bloom: a nationwide survey of U.S. urban tree planting initiatives (TPIs). *Urban For. Urban Green.* 61, 127006.
- Dumitru, A., Wendling, L., 2021. *Evaluating the Impact of Nature-Based Solutions: A Handbook for Practitioners*. Luxembourg.
- Eggermont, H., Balian, E., Azevedo, J.M., Beumer, V., Brodin, T., Claudet, J., Fady, B., Grube, M., Keune, H., Lamarque, P., Reuter, K., Smith, M., van Ham, C., Weisser, W., Le Roux, X., 2015. Nature-based solutions: new influence for environmental management and research in Europe. *GAIA* 24 (4), 243–248.
- Endreny, T.A., 2018. Strategically growing the urban forest will improve our world. *Nat. Commun.* 9 (1), 1160.
- European Commission, 2015. *Towards an EU Research and Innovation policy agenda for Nature-Based Solutions & Re-Naturing Cities*. Final report of the Horizon 2020 Expert Group on “Nature-Based Solutions and Re-Naturing Cities”. Brussels.
- FAO, 2016. *Guidelines on urban and peri-urban forestry*. FAO Forestry Paper, Vol. 178, Rome.
- FAO, 2018. *Global Forest Resources Assessment 2020: Terms and Definitions*. Forest Resources Assessment Working Paper, Vol. 188, Rome.
- Fischer, A.P., 2018. Forest landscapes as social-ecological systems and implications for management. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 177, 138–147.
- Gašević, D., Djurić, D., Devedžić, V., 2006. *Model Driven Architecture and Ontology Development*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Grabowski, Z., McPhearson, T., Matsler, A., Groffman, P., Pickett, S., 2022. What is green infrastructure? A study of definitions in US city planning. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.2445>.
- Gómez-Pérez, A., Fernández-López, M., Corcho, O., 2004. *Ontological Engineering with examples from the areas of Knowledge Management, e-Commerce and the Semantic Web*. Springer, London.
- Hanson, H., Wickenberg, B., Olsson, J., 2020. Working on the boundaries—how do science use and interpret the nature-based solution concept? *Land Use Policy* 90, 104302.
- Hitzler, P., Kröttsch, M., Parsia, B., Patel-Schneider, P.F., Rudolph, S., 2012. *OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Primer (Second Edition)*. Retrieved September 1st, 2021 from (<https://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-owl2-primer-20121211/>).
- Holt, A., Mears, M., Maltby, L., Warren, P., 2015. Understanding spatial patterns in the production of multiple urban ecosystem services. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 16, 33–46.
- Janssen, I., Rosu, A., 2015. Undeveloped green space and free-time physical activity in 11 to 13-year-old children. *Int. J. Behav. Nutr. Phys. Act.* 12 (26) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-015-0187-3>.
- Kaplański, P., 2011. Controlled English interface for knowledge bases. *Stud. Inform.* 32 (2A), 485–494.
- Kok, C.B., Osmond, P., Peters, A., 2016. A green infrastructure typology matrix to support urban microclimate studies. *Procedia Eng.* 169, 183–190.
- Konijnendijk, C., 2003. A decade of urban forestry in Europe. *For. Policy Econ.* 5 (2), 173–186.
- Langemeyer, J., Baró, F., 2021. Nature-based solutions as nodes of green-blue infrastructure networks: a cross-scale, co-creation approach. *Nat.-Based Solut.* 1, 100006.
- Lausch, A., Erasmí, S., King, D., Magdon, P., Heurich, M., 2016. Understanding forest health with remote sensing -part I—a review of spectral traits. *Process. Remote-Sens. Charact. Remote Sens.* 8 (12), 1029.
- Lehmann, I., Mathey, J., Rößler, S., Bräuer, A., Goldberg, V., 2014. Urban vegetation structure types as a methodological approach for identifying ecosystem services – application to the analysis of micro-climatic effects. *Ecol. Indic.* 42, 58–72.
- Marando, F., Salvatori, E., Sebastiani, A., Fusaro, L., Manes, F., 2019. Regulating ecosystem services and green infrastructure: assessment of Urban Heat Island effect mitigation in the municipality of Rome, Italy. *Ecol. Model.* 392, 92–102.

- Münzinger, M., Prechtel, N., Behnisch, M., 2022. Mapping the urban forest in detail: From LiDAR point clouds to 3D tree models. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 74, 127637.
- Nature4Cities, 2018. D1.1 – NBS multi-scalar and multi-thematic typology and associated database. EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, grant No 730468. Retrieved January 20th, 2022 from (https://9e99b973-33ae-43f5-b05a-fbba8e8b1314.filesusr.com/ugd/55d29d_8813db2df690497e80740537b6a8a844.pdf).
- Nikolaïdis, N., Lilli, M., Kolokotsa, D., Somarakis, G., Stagakis, S., Lemaitre, F., 2019. Classification of nature-based solutions. In: Somarakis, G., Stagakis, S., Chrysoulakis, N. (Eds.), *ThinkNature Nature-Based Solutions Handbook*. ThinkNature project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 730338. doi:10.26225/jerv-w202.
- Nissen, S., 2008. Urban transformation from public and private space to spaces of hybrid character. *Czech Sociol. Rev.* 44 (6), 1129–1149.
- Nowak, D., Maco, S., Binkley, M., 2018. i-Tree: global tools to assess tree benefits and risks to improve forest management. *Arboric. Consult.* 51 (4), 10–13.
- Ordóñez, C., 2021. Governance lessons from Australian local governments for retaining and protecting urban forests as nature based solutions. *Nat. -Based Solut.* 1, 100004.
- Ordóñez, C., Duinker, P., 2010. Interpreting sustainability for urban forests. *Sustainability* 2, 1510–1522.
- Ortí, A., Casanelles-Abella, J., Chiron, F., Deguines, N., Hallikma, T., Jaksi, P., Kwiatkowska, P., Moretti, M., Muysshondt, B., Niinemets, Ü., Pinho, P., Pinto, M., Saar, P., Samson, R., Tryjanowski, P., Van Mensel, A., Laanisto, L., 2022. Negative relationship between woody species density and size of urban green spaces in seven European cities. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 74, 127650.
- Pauleit, S., Zölch, T., Hansen, R., Randrup, T., Konijnendijk van den Bosch, C., 2017. Nature-Based Solutions and Climate Change – Four Shades of Green. In: Kabisch, N., Korn, H., Stadler, J., Bonn, A. (Eds.), *Nature-Based Solutions to Climate Change Adaptation in Urban Areas. Theory and Practice of Urban Sustainability Transitions*. Springer, Cham, pp. 29–49.
- Romijn, E., Ainembabazi, J., Wijaya, A., Herold, M., Angelsen, A., Verchot, L., Murdiyasar, D., 2013. Exploring different forest definitions and their impact on developing REDD+ reference emission levels: a case study for Indonesia. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 33, 246–259.
- Scheuer, S., Jache, J., Sumfleth, L., Wellmann, T., Haase, D., 2021a. Creating accessible evidence bases: opportunities through the integration of interactive tools into literature review synthesis. *MethodsX* 8, 101558.
- Scheuer, S., Jache, J., Wellmann, T., Wolff, M., Haase, D., 2021b. Report on a novel standardised Sino-European UFBS typology. Retrieved January 1st, 2022 from (https://clearinghouseproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/D1_1_Report_on_a_novel_standardised_Sino_European_UFBS_typology_V1.pdf).
- Seganti, A., Kaplański, P., Zarzycki, P., 2016. Collaborative Editing of Ontologies Using Fluent Editor and Ontarion. In: Tamma, V., Dragoni, M., Gonçalves, R., Ławrynowicz, A. (Eds.), *Ontology Engineering. OWLED 2015: Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, 9557. Springer, Cham, pp. 45–55.
- Smith, A.C., Berry, P.M., Harrison, P.A., 2016. Sustainable Ecosystem Management. In: Potschin, M., Jax, K. (Eds.), *OpenNESS Ecosystem Services Reference Book*. EC FP7 Grant Agreement no. 308428. Retrieved February 5th, 2020 from (<http://www.openness-project.eu/library/reference-book>).
- Steenberg, J.W.N., Millward, A.A., Duinker, P.N., Nowak, D.J., Robinson, P.J., 2015. Neighbourhood-scale urban forest ecosystem classification. *J. Environ. Manag.* 163, 134–145.
- Sure, Y., Staab, S., Studer, R., 2009. Ontology Engineering Methodology. In: Staab, S., Studer, R. (Eds.), *Handbook on Ontologies*, second ed. Springer, Dordrecht, pp. 135–152.
- Taylor, L., Hochuli, D., 2017. Defining greenspace: multiple uses across multiple disciplines. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 158, 25–38.
- Turner-Skoff, J.B., Cavender, N., 2019. The benefits of trees for livable and sustainable communities. *Plants, People, Planet* 1, 323–335.
- Uschold, M., Grüninger, M., 1996. Ontologies: principles, methods and applications. *Knowl. Eng. Rev.* 11 (2), 93–155.
- Uschold, M., King, M., 1995. Towards a methodology for building ontologies. In: Skuce, D. (Ed.), *IJCAI'95 Workshop on Basic Ontological Issues in Knowledge Sharing*. Montreal, Canada, pp. 6.1–6.10.
- Vieira, J., Matos, P., Mexia, T., Silva, P., Lopes, N., Freitas, C., Correia, O., Santos-Reis, M., Branquinho, C., Pinho, P., 2018. Green spaces are not all the same for the provision of air purification and climate regulation services: the case of urban parks. *Environ. Res.* 160, 306–313.
- Villa, F., Athanasiades, I.N., Rizzoli, A.E., 2009. Modelling with knowledge: A review of emerging semantic approaches to environmental modelling. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 24, 577–587.
- Violle, C., Navas, M.-L., Vile, D., Kazakou, E., Fortunel, C., Hummel, I., Garnier, E., 2007. Let the concept of trait be functional! *Oikos* 116 (5), 882–892.
- Vlaamse Land Maatschappij, 2019. Green and Blue Infrastructure for Grey Peri-Urban Landscapes. Retrieved January 1st, 2021 from (<https://green4grey.be/en>).
- Vogt, J., 2020. Urban forests as social-ecological systems. In: Goldstein, M., Della Sala, D. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of the World's Biomes*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 58–70.
- Walters, M., Sinnett, D., 2021. Achieving tree canopy cover targets: A case study of Bristol, UK. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 65, 127296.
- Wellmann, T., Haase, D., Knapp, S., Salbach, C., Selsam, P., Lausch, A., 2018. Urban land use intensity assessment: The potential of spatio-temporal spectral traits with remote sensing. *Ecol. Indic.* 85, 190–203.
- WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2016. Urban green spaces and health. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Zakharova, L., Meyer, K.M., Seifan, M., 2019. Trait-based modelling in ecology: a review of two decades of research. *Ecol. Model.* 407, 108703.
- Zürcher, N., 2017. Assessing the ecosystem service deliverable: the critical role of the urban tree inventory. In: Pearlmutter, D., Calfapietra, C., Samson, R., O'Brien, L., Ostoić, S., Sanesi, G., del Amo, R. (Eds.), *The Urban Forest*. Cham, Switzerland, pp. 101–110.